

BLENDING OF POLY(LACTIC ACID) AND ACRYLONITRILE BUTADIENE STYRENE FOR USE AS BIOCOMPOSITE MATRIX

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1 Introduction

As the world populations continue to grow, the use of sustainable industrial practices becomes more important. Currently, the world's dependence on petroleum resources, which are finite by their nature, does not serve the sustainable practices that are required [1]. Petroleum resources are utilized in areas such as synthetic materials, which are extensively used as an inexpensive, robust alternative to natural materials.

For this reason, many research efforts have gone towards the development of bio-based alternatives to synthetic materials. The term bio-based is not to be confused with biodegradable, which a polymer may be one, both or none, as depicted in figure 1. Although bio-based materials are currently available, their use in commercial applications is very limited. This is due to several barriers preventing them from regular use in commercial products [2]. In terms of performance for specific durable applications, many have insufficient performance values in one or more properties, including toughness, heat stability or strength. From an economic standpoint, there is only one bio-plastic that is currently truly cost competitive with petroleum-based polymers, and that is poly(lactic acid) (PLA). The main performance drawbacks for PLA are toughness and heat stability. It is a very brittle polymer, and begins to warp under relatively low temperatures, which prevents its widespread use [3].

To serve as a solution to the aforementioned problems, PLA may be blended with other polymers of higher performance. In terms of bio-based content, even if the blending partner is petroleum based, each percentage of PLA used in the final blend is one less that contributes to petroleum use. It is with this in mind that this work aims to blend PLA

with petroleum based acrylonitrile butadiene styrene, (ABS). This may allow for a good balance of performance, from the ABS, and bio-based content, from the PLA.

2 Currently Used Industrial Plastics

Plastics have become a very pervasive material in many industries. This is due to the relative strength of the material in relation to its cost. For increasingly general applications, plastics are the material of choice. Plastics can be categorized based on cost and performance. Generally speaking, the cost increases in proportion to the performance of the material. Low performing, but inexpensive plastics are known as commodity polymers, and are used extensively for non-structural, low performance applications. This includes domestic products and packaging. This category is comprised of well-known polymers such as polypropylene (PP), polystyrene (PS), polyethylene (PE), poly (ethylene terephthalate), and poly (vinyl chloride) (PVC) [4]. In terms of performance, plastics that are superior to these aforementioned plastics are known as engineering plastics. They are used for structural and semi-structural in addition to high performance applications. These polymers are known for their high strength, impact resistance, and in some cases, their thermal resistance. The list of polymers that belong to this category is extensive, and includes polymers such as nylon, polycarbonate (PC), poly (ethyl ethyl ketone) (PEEK), and poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA). As mentioned, these polymers are higher performing, but that performance comes at a cost. Falling between these two categories is acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), which has attractive properties at a fairly economical price point.

3 Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) and its Uses

ABS is a terpolymer composed of acrylonitrile, butadiene, and styrene. Due to its composition, it has a balance of properties, which can be tailored by adjusting the ratio of each constituent [5]. Due to these facts along with its cost and relative performance, ABS is widely used in industry for semi-structural and housing applications [5]. This is seen in two major industries. In the electronics industry, ABS is used for casings, component housings and internal parts. In the automotive industry, ABS is used for interior trim applications where the material may be subjected to wear-and-tear and be required to have a high durability.

Like many common plastics, ABS is a petroleum-based material. As previously mentioned, the use of petroleum is an unsustainable practice and steps need to be taken to build strategies and practices that are more sustainable. As part of this, bio-plastics have come to the forefront as a potential viable sustainable material.

4 Bio-plastics

Bio-plastics are called such for their meeting one of two criteria: bio-based content or biodegradability [6]. Plastics that contain bio-based content offset the amount of petroleum that is used in materials manufacturing. As a corollary, the amount of greenhouse gasses (GHGs) that is expelled into the atmosphere is reduced. This is done by creating a carbon cycle that redistributes carbon from the atmosphere into plant material, which is used to create bioplastics. Thus, there is no net increase in carbon.

Biodegradable plastics address the issue of landfilling. Landfilling has been shown to be a special issue as the world's population continues to grow. In addition, landfills have been known to pollute the ground water [7]. By developing biodegradable plastics that are environmentally benign, these landfilling issues are resolved as the plastic can be decomposed instead of discarded into a landfill.

Generally, bio-plastics can be bio-based, biodegradable, or both. The most notable polymers that are fully biodegradable and bio-based are

poly(lactic acid) (PLA) and poly(hydroxyl butyrate) (PHB). However, there are several polymers that can fulfill application requirements of either bio-based or biodegradable.

There are several polymers that are biodegradable, yet still petroleum based. These polymers are useful in addressing the issue of landfilling. Although they are not offsetting the carbon increase in materials, they do offer a solution to the petroleum-intense practice of landfilling.

On the other hand, there have been recent developments introducing bio-based, non-biodegradable plastics. These are generally a bio-based version of a currently used petro-based polymer. For example, bio-polyethylene has been developed recently that is derived from bio-based carbon. The chemical structure is still that of petro-based polyethylene, and thus does not facilitate the mechanism of biodegradation.

The polymers that are either bio-based or biodegradable, but not both, may be utilized in certain specific applications that it is well suited for. As with any major change/disruption to an industry, many will be slow to adopt practices. Thus, these particular polymers will be well utilized as small steps toward total sustainability will be beneficial.

5 Poly(lactic acid)

As previously mentioned, poly(lactic acid) (PLA) is one of the most notable polymers that are both bio-based and biodegradable. The reason for its potential includes several factors. The biggest of these, however, is price. Whereas many biopolymers are many times more expensive than their petroleum-based counter parts, poly(lactic acid) is cost competitive [8]. This has been achieved through many years of increasing production, and increases in polymerization efficiency.

The performance of PLA is actually superior to current commodity plastics in many aspects. The performance areas where it is lacking – and the reasons for its barrier from large-scale use – is in its thermal stability and toughness. Generally, PLA is a brittle polymer, with low impact strength [9]. This is holding it from being used more readily as a durable polymer. In addition, it has a glass transition temperature (T_g) around 55°C, causing it to become

structurally unstable above this temperature [9]. Although this temperature is well above ambient, almost every material application has the possibility to be subjected to higher temperatures, and thus it cannot be used. For example, disposable water bottles seem to be a good fit for PLA, as it has a high tensile strength. However, if it were left in a car in the sun on a warm day, the bottle would distort to the point that the bottle may be unusable.

Poly(lactic acid) is an aliphatic polyester and is found in one of two stereospecific configurations, D- and L- enantiomers [10]. The performance of PLA can be tailored much like that of ABS by adjusting the proportion of enantiomers in the final product. However, unlike ABS, this is a chemically challenging and cost prohibitive task.

Poly(lactic acid), which is comprised of the fundamental building block of lactic acid, can be synthesized through carbohydrate fermentation. Although chemical synthesis is another possible route for PLA production, fermentation is the more used method, as it is more economically viable. The components used for fermentation are starch and sugar extracted from corn.

Processing of PLA is generally accomplished through melt processing. Unlike heat forming, where the polymer is brought above the (T_g) but lower than melting temperature (T_m), melt processing completely melts the polymer [10]. PLA is suited for melt processing, as it has a high melt index and low melt strength. Thus, PLA is generally injection molded into final shapes. Injection molding is a fast, economical, and reliable method that has been honed as the most used method of plastic forming.

PLA is a semi-crystalline polymer, which means that its chain structure contains both highly oriented crystalline phases in addition to highly random amorphous phases [10]. The degree of potential crystallization depends on the chirality of the polymer. PLA has a very slow crystallization time, meaning that the chains require more time and energy to configure themselves into the ordered structure of crystallinity [10]. This has an impact on the final properties of the material, as the crystallinity has been shown to affect the thermal stability, and toughness.

6 Polymer Blending Theory

Blending of two polymers is done while in the molten state. Generally, the use of an extruder allows the heat and shearing required for such a process [11]. In many cases, the blending of two polymers results in low adhesion between the phases, and thus an immiscible polymer blend [11]. With a low adhesion, mechanical properties will be decreased, and the result will be a generally poor performing polymer. In addition to adhesion, interphasial tension is a material property that dictates performance [11]. With optimal tension between the phases, a better dispersion of one polymer in the other can be achieved [11]. By increasing adhesion and optimizing tension between the phases, the blend can reach a miscible state, meaning that there is compatibility between the polymers.

The miscibility of two polymers depends on miscibility 'windows' [11]. Thermodynamics of the processing and polymers dictates the miscibility windows. In the general sense, like polymers will blend well together. When blending two fairly compatible polymers, or in composites, with fiber and polymers, the final properties may be estimated using the rule of mixtures. Basically, the final properties will be similar to the weight averaged property value between the two (or more) constituents. However, this rule fails in estimating the blending of non-compatible constituents. The final properties of immiscible blends can be much lower than that of the individual polymers [11].

8 Natural Fibers

Composite materials combine two or more materials together in order to produce a material that has properties unlike its constituents [12]. The best uses of composite materials involve the addition of materials that have complimentary properties. For example, in glass fiber reinforced materials, the glass fiber provided the final material with a high strength and stiffness while the polymer matrix provides the toughness, elongation, and processing capabilities. In addition to glass fibers, carbon fibers have also been used in specialty applications that require a very high strength and stiffness, while also weight is a large factor. Carbon fiber materials are used in high-end bicycle frames, racing car bodies,

as well as other high performance, and low weight applications. Increasingly since the 1990's, natural fibers have been investigated for their ability to be used for natural fiber applications [12]. Figure 2 depicts the categorization of fibers from their derivatives.

There are several advantages to creating a well performing composite material using natural fibers. The first, and the underlying theme of this paper, is to increase the sustainability of the material. Natural fibers are natural carbon sequestration units. They require carbon to grow, trapping it in their structure. When the end of life of the material comes, the fibers biodegrade, releasing the carbon back into the atmosphere. This cycle, not including transportation and harvesting processes, is carbon neutral. This is much more sustainable than releasing an already sequestered carbon source in petroleum.

Natural fibers can be grown for their use in these materials, but they can also be obtained as the by-product of other agricultural processes. For example, soy hull is the discarded outer enclosure of the soybean. These by-products have been traditionally used as animal feed, or simply discarded of. For this reason, they are extremely inexpensive to obtain. By using natural fibers in composite materials, a new value has been put into these materials. This is a value added application in the agricultural industry, as well as reducing costs in the manufacturing industry.

Natural fibers can be compared to glass fibers, which are currently used in 95% of fiber reinforcement in polymer resins [13]. Although natural fibers do not have the strength or modulus of glass fibers, they do hold some advantages. As mentioned, they are much less costly than glass fibers – orders of magnitude less. In addition, they have a bulk density that is much less than glass fibers, allowing weight savings [13]. The final consideration that is afforded natural fibers is their biodegradability. Being plant based, these fibers are 100% biodegradable, and when coupled with a polymer matrix that is also biodegradable, the product is 100% biodegradable.

Natural fibers found in plants are lingo-cellulosic in nature. That is to say that the main constituents are cellulose, lignin, and hemicellulose. They can be categorized into wood and non-wood fibers, non-

wood being the focus of this paper [13]. Non-wood fibers may be split up by which part of the plant that they are obtained. Bast fibers are obtained from the stalk, leaf fibers from the leaves, and seed/fruit fibers from off growth of the plant. Grass and straw fibers require less processing after growth to abstract the fiber (Figure 3).

There are several challenges that come with creating natural fiber composites with desirable performance. The biggest problem is poor adhesion between the fiber and the matrix. This can lead to other problems, such as fiber pullout and void formation [13]. In all cases, these characteristics will lead to a poor performing material. As the fibers are obtained from several agricultural sources, the quality can vary dramatically as there are changes in climate, soil, and groundwater conditions. A problem that comes from this is trying to obtain agricultural fibers that produce uniform materials in their performance and characteristics. The final challenge of creating natural fiber composites is that the fibers are hydrophilic and absorb water, severely worsening the performance of the material.

Mohanty et al. [13] have addressed this problem by creating a tri-corner approach to efficient natural fiber composite development. First comes efficient bio-fiber treatment. This includes low cost alkali or bleaching that will increase the compatibility of the fiber and the polymeric matrix. The second step is modification of the polymer matrix to again enhance the compatibility of the composite constituents. In the final step, proper and efficient processing parameters and mechanisms are chosen to increase mixing and reactivity while decreasing thermal degradation of the polymer.

9 Materials and Methods

The PLA (Ingeo 3801X) that was used for blending in this research was purchased from NatureWorks LLC, USA. It has a melt flow index (MFI) of approximately 8 g/10 min. It is a high impact grade of PLA, with several fillers and additives to increase its properties. Among added elements are a crystal accelerant, nucleating agent and impact modifier. The addition of these elements has rendered the PLA less than 100% bio-based and non-biodegradable. This material was chosen as the biodegradability is of lesser importance than a viable bio-based

polymer. In addition, although it is not 100% bio-based, the improved properties mean that blending with ABS is more likely to result in a well performing polymer.

The ABS was obtained from Styron™ under the tradename Magnum 1150 EM. The Butadiene content is approximately 40%, causing the MFI to be 0.9 g/10 min. This high rubber content ABS was chosen as a blend partner after analysis of solubility parameter according to Higgins Flory blending theory [14]. By studying the solubility parameter of each of the polymers, and choosing grades so that the solubility parameters match as closely as possible, the likelihood of producing a well-performing polymer is increased. PLA has a solubility parameter of $9.58 \text{ cal}^{1/2} \text{ cm}^{3/2}$ [15], according to literature, the solubility parameter of ABS is dependent on its butadiene content [5]. Having a butadiene content around 40% produces an ABS very close to $9.58 \text{ cal}^{1/2} \text{ cm}^{3/2}$ [5]. In addition to solubility analysis, this grade of ABS is a high impact tough grade. These are the performance areas, which PLA is deficient, and so this improves the likelihood of producing a tough polymer blend. The soy stalk was obtained locally in Ontario, Canada. The fiber sizes varied, but were approximately 6-8 mm in length. They were used as is in the blending process.

To ensure moisture content below 100 ppm, which is recommended to avoid viscosity degradation, all materials were dried in an 80°C oven for at least 3 hours prior to blending.

The crystallization of PLA was studied through differences in molding temperature. The PLA was molded on an Arburg injection molder at 30°C, 60°C, and 90°C. This led to changes in the crystallization of the PLA.

The two polymers and fiber were melt blended and molded in a microcompounder and micro-injection molder. This equipment utilizes twin co-rotating screws that are 150 mm in length and have an L/D of 18. For compounding, the screws were set to 100 RPM, the barrel temperature was 220°C and the residence time was 2 min. Test specimen were made in the micro-injection molder for characterization of properties including mechanical and thermal.

Tensile and flexural testing was performed using a universal testing machine, according to ASTM

standards D638 and D790, respectively. The impact strength testing was completed using the notched Izod method on a Testing Machine Inc (TMI) machine according to ASTM D256. Thermal testing included dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The DMA was carried out according to ASTM D4065. The DSC of the samples was ascertained on heat/cool/heat mode. Morphology was studied using a scanning electron microscope. Mechanical testing included 5 samples per testing set while thermal sampled 3 per set, the average value and standard deviation taken for each.

10 Results and Discussion

The crystallization of PLA was studied by varying the mold temperature to induce an annealing effect [17]. This led to changes in the crystalline content of the PLA polymer. With higher molding temperature, more energy is provided to the chains, and thus they are freer to move and orient themselves in the crystalline state. This had a profound influence on the mechanical properties, causing an increase in the elongation at break and impact strength [16]. This was due to the more flexible amorphous regions allowing the absorption of mechanical energy. Crystallization of the polymer tightly constricted the polymer chains, decreasing the propagation energy to failure. The crystallinity and mechanical properties were analysed from two varying points of view. Both properties as a function of mold temperature and as a function of time were carefully studied. It was found that although the higher mold temperatures produced more crystallinity and lower overall mechanical properties, the stability of the structure was much higher than that of the lower mold temperatures [16]. The 90°C mold did not greatly change in properties over time, whereas there was a decrease in properties over time seen in the samples molded at 30°C and 60°C. The effect on the mechanical properties was compounded by dual phase behavior of the chains [16]. The highly crystalline material has much more rigidity in the crystalline phase, but because there is a low amorphous volume, it is pressured greatly by the crystalline phase, and thus acts as a quasi-crystalline phase. In lower mold temperatures, where the amorphous phase volume is much higher, it tends to act more freely than the amorphous phase of the

highly crystalline samples. The amorphous phase allowed the polymer chains more mobility when strained, and thus the polymer was able to absorb more energy during testing. This is what ultimately led to the high impact and elongation at break of the polymers.

Studies on the blending of PLA/ABS include analysis of several parameters of blending. Blending in various ratios from neat PLA to neat ABS allowed the evaluation of properties across a wide range of formulation (figure 3), and comparison between those properties and neat constituents [17]. It was shown that as the volume of interface increases, and therefore the interaction between the two polymer increases, the properties decrease [17]. This indicates that without blending aids such as compatibilizers, these two polymers are not miscible, as shown by the morphology of impact strength tested samples (figure 4).

By taking the material after full development and making it into a bio-fiber reinforced composite has several effects and advantages. The fiber used comes from 100% bio-based resources and its addition into the material will increase the overall bio-content by weight. Comparing the fiber to the plastic itself, it is much less dense. Therefore, moulding the same part (i.e. same volume) will cause a light weighting effect. Many molders and manufacturers are interested in this as performance can be improved while saving cost. The addition of bio-fiber is expected to increase the glass transition temperature, which can in turn raise the HDT of the material, a very desirable effect in this situation.

The mechanical properties are affected by the addition of 30%/wt of soy stalk, as presented in table 1. The impact strength and elongation at break are decreased as a result of the fiber. On the other hand, the HDT and modulus are increased. Both of these results are expected as the addition of a reinforcing agent causes the material to become more brittle. With this increase in the brittleness of the material, the stiffness is increased. As mentioned, the HDT is increased through the change in the glass transition temperature. The properties are again only slightly increased due again to incompatibility. Here, a third component is added, and adhesion is not present between any of the phases in the material. The properties given after adding the bio-fiber into the uncompatibilized matrix is only an indication of

resulting properties after further development of a better performing and compatibilized blend.

The properties of both blending the polymers and the addition of fiber to create a bio-composite rests on the adhesion present between phases. Therefore, the successful development of a bio-based material is centered on increasing the interfacial adhesion. Increase the adhesion, and the properties will follow suit.

11 Conclusion

In this study, research was completed to assess the feasibility of bio-fiber/bio-plastic based composites. First, the biopolymer was studied in terms of its mechanical properties and thermal properties in relation to its processing conditions. It was found that the temperature of the mold had a profound effect on the crystallinity of the PLA. This, in turn affected the mechanical properties, where the high crystallinity samples had lower toughness, but a much more stable configuration over time. The high temperature molded samples had better toughness, as the amorphous regions were able to better absorb the energy, but was also less stable, and changes were seen over time.

The blending of PLA/ABS was also studied as a potential for a bio-composite matrix material. Miscibility analysis showed that in all ratios, there is very little compatibility between the polymers. This, in turn, leads to low adhesion between phases, and an overall poor performing polymer. As the blend ratios approached 1:1, the properties were the lowest, confirming the low adhesion. This is true because at roughly equal volumes in the blend, the phases become co-continuous, where there is no more major/minor phase. This is the configuration that has the highest interaction area of polymer phases, which explains why the properties are the lowest at these ratios [11].

Finally, soy stalk was used as a bio-fiber reinforcement for bio-composite development. Using a fiber-reinforcing agent has been known to increase the stiffness of the composite in relation to the polymer, and this was found to be the case in the addition of soy stalk to the PLA/ABS blend. In addition, the impact strength was decreased, as expected.

This work serves as the basis for the development of a bio-composite from bioplastics and bio-fibers. With this development and use of this material, petroleum use may be offset, and greener, more sustainable products may be made.

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Fig. 1. Bioplastic categorization scheme. Redrawn after [17]

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Fig. 2. Bio-fiber categorization scheme. Redrawn after [13]

Fig. 3. Impact strength and elongation at break for various blending ratios of PLA/ABS

Fig. 4. Scanning electron microscopy for PLA/ABS (50:50)

Table 1. Mechanical properties of PLA/ABS blend with and without soy stalk

Composition of Blend/Composite	Tensile Strength [MPa]	Tensile Modulus [GPa]	Elongation at Break [%]	Flexural Strength [MPa]	Flexural Modulus [GPa]	Impact Strength [J/m]
PLA/ABS (70:30)	27.9 ± 1.34	2.34 ± 0.01	4.92 ± 1.31	44.4 ± 0.89	2.56 ± 0.06	43.43 ± 12.74
PLA/ABS (70:30) + 30% Soy Stalk	30.9 ± 0.54	3.91 ± 0.07	1.17 ± 0.07	46.06 ± 2.01	4.60 ± 0.12	36.82 ± 8.9